

FLEXIBLE MULTISTAGE DESIGN WITH BOTH SAFETY AND EFFICACY USING THE PREDICTED PROBABILITY

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ABSTRACT

Safety and efficacy are common endpoints in phase II oncology trials as these are still under investigation early on in drug development but few flexible methods exist to design such a trial with arbitrary interim analyses for both. We present a novel statistical method that uses Bayesian predictive probability to determine cutoffs for independent or correlated response and nontoxicity for a trial at each stage and evaluates the expected performance using a non-homogeneous Markov chain. We search over the set of posterior and predictive probability thresholds at which discrete cutoffs change to find optimal and minimax designs for this type of trial. Our results show the limitations of calculating sample sizes and interim analysis cutoffs using a single efficacy endpoint compared to using our method. Using our method to increase the frequency of interim analyses also improves the maximum and expected enrollment in the trial. The Bayesian predictive probability framework applied here facilitates flexible trial design in terms of the relative stringency, frequency, and timing of interim analyses to design properly powered, robust trials of safety and efficacy.

Keywords: Clinical trials, Bayesian predictive probability, multiple endpoints, Markov process, odds ratio, phase II trial

1. INTRODUCTION

Phase II studies provide initial data on drug effect and safety to guide further development. In oncology, they are often single-arm studies to estimate efficacy at a fixed dose established in phase I development. A poor result in terms of low response or high toxicity can lead the sponsor to stop developing a compound for a particular indication. During such clinical studies, there can be advantages to running interim analyses on patient response or toxicity and terminating the trial early if success appears improbable, sparing the sponsor from unnecessary cost and patients from unnecessary exposure to the drug.

Many strategies exist for planning and conducting interim analyses for phase II studies, including Simon's two-stage design (Simon, 1989) which allows for a single interim analysis of one efficacy endpoint when a study can be terminated early for futility. In phase II studies the safety profile of the drug may not be well understood in the patient population of interest, so there is a possibility the sponsor will choose to terminate the study at the interim analysis for safety reasons even if the drug's efficacy appears promising. This possibility, if improperly accounted for at the design stage, will result in an under-powered study. In addition, the practical

limitations of study design and execution may limit when an interim analysis can be carried out, or provide the opportunity for more than one interim analysis. For these reasons, in this paper we propose a new method for a trial with an arbitrary number of interim analyses of both efficacy and toxicity based on Bayesian principles of predictive probability of trial success on these two criteria.

We continue with a brief discussion of three existing strategies with interim analyses in the following subsections in order to motivate the development of our method.

1.1. Simon's Two-Stage Design

Simon's two-stage design (Simon, 1989) is one of the classic methods for group sequential design of a phase II trial for efficacy. Under this design, there is one interim analysis of a single endpoint during the trial when it can be terminated early for futility. If the trial passes this interim analysis, then the full sample size of the study is recruited and analyzed, at which point trial success or failure can be determined. The user here only needs to specify an unacceptable response rate p_0 , an acceptable response rate p_1 , desired type 1 error rate α , and power $1 - \beta$. Using this information, Simon's design provides solutions for calculating the sample size n_1 and response cutoff r_1 at the interim analysis and at the final stage (n and r) to achieve the desired type 1 error rate and power, either optimizing the expected sample size under the null (optimal design) or the sample size in the final stage (minimax).

1.2. Bayesian Predictive Probability Design

Lee and Liu introduced the method for Bayesian predictive probability design (2008). Their method also tests a single efficacy endpoint but is more flexible in terms of the number and timing of interim analyses during the trial. In this setting, the user specifies an acceptable response rate, p_1 , an unacceptable response rate, p_0 , and desired bounds on type 1 error α and type 2 error β which are used to determine the sample size N_{max} and number of responses at the end of the trial. With the help of prior probability of response (which can be conservatively based on p_0), they can then calculate the predictive probability of eventual trial success based on any possible number of responses at any point in the trial. If, for a given number of responses, the predictive probability of trial success falls below a pre-defined threshold, then the trial is terminated early. While this predictive probability approach allows an arbitrary number of interim analyses, this design only achieves optimal trial performance if the maximum number of interim analyses are performed.

In phase II studies, the safety profile of a new drug is still under investigation and the trial protocol may include criteria for ending the trial based on the toxicities observed during the trial. If the sample size for the study has been calculated on the basis of the efficacy alone then these stopping criteria for observed toxicities will prevent the trial from achieving the desired power. In addition, the investigators may lack rigorous rules for defining the stopping criteria for observed toxicities without a joint statistical framework for analyzing both efficacy and safety.

1.3. Bryant and Day

Bryant and Day (1995) introduced a method for a two-stage study similar to the Simon's design but which incorporates testing of both efficacy and nontoxicity into the interim and final analyses. Under this framework, the user specifies acceptable rates for response P_{R1} and

nontoxicity P_{T1} and unacceptable rates P_{R0}, P_{T0} with the option to specify an odds ratio ϕ between response and nontoxicity to model the scenario where they are dependent events. From these, the Bryant and Day method calculates the sample size N_1 and stopping rules for response C_{R1} and nontoxicity C_{T1} at an interim analysis and at study completion N_2, C_{R2}, C_{T2} for either an optimal or a minimax design. In addition, they provide bounds on the effect of the odds ratio ϕ on power and type 1 error rate.

We draw inspiration from all these existing methods to accommodate flexible design and testing for both safety and efficacy at an arbitrary number of stages in a phase II trial. Here we present a flexible multistage design for both safety and efficacy using a Bayesian predictive probability in Section 2. Users have the option of modelling the efficacy response and toxicity as either dependent or independent events. In addition, our method is able to optimize trial performance for any predefined interim analyses. An illustrative example is used in Section [Error! Reference source not found.](#) to showcase the developed method, and the discussion is followed in Section 4.

2. METHODS

2.1. Hypotheses for two endpoints with multiple stages

With two endpoints, we consider 4 possible hypotheses regarding the probability of response to a given drug or therapy, p_R , and the probability of nontoxicity p_T . They are as follows:

H_{00} : unacceptable response $p_R \leq p_{R0}$, unacceptable nontoxicity $p_T \leq p_{T0}$

H_{01} : unacceptable response $p_R \leq p_{R0}$, acceptable nontoxicity $p_T \geq p_{T1}$

H_{10} : acceptable response $p_R \geq p_{R1}$, unacceptable nontoxicity $p_T \leq p_{T0}$

H_{11} : acceptable response $p_R \geq p_{R1}$, acceptable nontoxicity $p_T \geq p_{T1}$

with $p_{R0} < p_{R1}$ and $p_{T0} < p_{T1}$. Let x_{Rl} be the number of responses and x_{Tl} be the number of nontoxicities at the end of stage l . We compare these against predetermined cutoffs, C_{Rl} and C_{Tl} , to decide whether to proceed to the next stage and enroll additional participants or terminate the trial early. The correct decision when any of $H_{00}, H_{01},$ or H_{10} are true is to terminate the trial. The correct decision when H_{11} is true is to recommend the drug for further study. We visualize this decision and the hypotheses at each trial stage in a matrix in [Figure 1](#).

2.2. Joint Testing

In joint testing there are two endpoints that must exceed a minimum threshold to claim success in the trial. We use response and nontoxicity as the two endpoints for testing but these could be any two endpoints.

2.2.1. Notation and hypotheses

With two endpoints, the hypotheses are as stated in Section 2.1. We define the expected type 1 and type 2 error probabilities under each hypothesis as:

$$P(\text{Trial success}|H_{00}) = \alpha_{00}$$

$$P(\text{Trial success}|H_{01}) = \alpha_{01}$$

$$P(\text{Trial success}|H_{10}) = \alpha_{10}$$

$$P(\text{Trial failure}|H_{11}) = 1 - \alpha_{11}.$$

The study design must satisfy the following constraints on type 1 and type 2 error:

$$\alpha_{01} \leq \alpha_R$$

$$\alpha_{10} \leq \alpha_T$$

$$1 - \alpha_{11} \leq \beta$$

where α_R , α_T , and β are bounds on type 1 and type 2 error specified by the user. α_{00} is not binding on either α_R or α_T since $\alpha_{00} \leq \min(\alpha_{10}, \alpha_{01})$.

Type 1 and type 2 error are controlled by deciding trial success, failure, and early termination by the count of responses observed, x_{Rl} , and the count of nontoxicities observed, x_{Tl} , out of the number of participants planned n_l at each stage l in a k -stage trial:

x_{Rl} : observed response count at stage $l \in \{1, \dots, k\}$

x_{Tl} : observed nontoxicity count at stage $l \in \{1, \dots, k\}$

n_l : planned sample size at stage $l \in \{1, \dots, k\}$.

In addition to the outcome of the trial, the accrual or number of individuals N enrolled in the study prior to termination (or completion) is also of interest. Therefore, in addition to α_{10} and α_{01} , the expected performance of a trial design is also described by the expected accrual under the null hypotheses. Since the expected accrual can differ under H_{01} and H_{10} , we summarize the expected trial accrual under the set of null hypotheses, E_Ω , as the worse of these two quantities.

$$E_{00} = E(N|H_{00})$$

$$E_{01} = E(N|H_{01})$$

$$E_{10} = E(N|H_{10})$$

$$E_{11} = E(N|H_{11})$$

$$E_\Omega = \max(E_{01}, E_{10})$$

We do not consider E_{00} since this is not binding, i.e. $E_{00} \leq \min(E_{01}, E_{10})$.

Similarly, we summarize the probability of early termination under the set of null hypotheses as PET_Ω :

$$PET_{00} = P(N < n_k|H_{00})$$

$$PET_{01} = P(N < n_k|H_{01})$$

$$PET_{10} = P(N < n_k|H_{10})$$

$$PET_{11} = P(N < n_k|H_{11})$$

$$PET_\Omega = \min(PET_{01}, PET_{10}).$$

Again, PET_{00} is not binding since $PET_{00} \geq \max(PET_{01}, PET_{10})$.

Generally, study designs with smaller E_Ω and larger PET_Ω while satisfying α_R , α_T , and β are more desirable as this reduces the cost to the sponsor and unnecessary treatment of study participants when any of H_{00} , H_{10} , or H_{01} is true. Similarly, study designs with larger E_{11} and smaller PET_{11} are desirable since this corresponds to a higher probability of advancing to the final stage of the trial when H_{11} is true. This notation is summarized in the matrix shown in Figure 2.

2.2.2. Predictive probability

We begin the calculation of predictive probability by defining the probability of observing i future responses given x_{Rl} current responses using the beta binomial distribution, with a_R and b_R as beta distribution priors:

$$P(Y_R = i | x_{Rl}): \text{beta binomial}(i; a_R + x_{Rl}, b_R + n_l - x_{Rl}, m_l) \\ = \binom{m_l}{i} \frac{B(i + a_R + x_{Rl}, m_l - i + b_R + n_l - x_{Rl})}{B(a_R + x_{Rl}, b_R + n_l - x_{Rl})}$$

where m_l is the number of patients remaining in the trial. Setting $a_R = p_{R0}$ and $b_R = 1 - p_{R0}$ correspond to a prior distribution for Y_R based on one observation with mean at the null probability p_{R0} .

Next, we define I_{Ri} as an indicator for whether the posterior probability that the true response rate p_R is greater than the null response rate p_{R0} given $x_{Rl} + i$ total responses at the end of the trial is greater than some threshold θ_{RT} .

$$I_{Ri}: \text{Indicator } \{(\text{posterior probability of } p_R > p_{R0}) > \theta_{RT}\} \\ = I \left[\left(\int_{p_{R0}}^1 \frac{p^{a_R + x_{Rl} + i - 1} (1 - p)^{b_R + n_k - x_{Rl} - i - 1}}{B(a_R + x_{Rl} + i, b_R + n_k - x_{Rl} - i)} dp \right) > \theta_{RT} \right]$$

We then define the predictive probability of eventual trial success (not accounting for the possibility of early termination of the trial) after the final stage when currently at stage l as

$$PP_{Rl} = \sum_{i=0}^{m_l = n_k - n_l} P(Y_R = i | x_{Rl}) I_{Ri}$$

which is the sum of the probability of every possible number of future responses i given x_{Rl} responses observed so far at stage l times an indicator I_{Ri} . PP_{Rl} is essentially the probability that there will be sufficient responses at the end of the trial to claim success, given the current number of responses.

The predictive probability of nontoxicity PP_{Tl} is also nearly identical, except that p_{T0} is the null-hypothesis probability of nontoxicity, a_T and b_T are the beta-binomial distribution priors, θ_{TT} is the posterior probability threshold, and θ_{TL} is the predictive probability threshold. We use PP_{Rl} and PP_{Tl} to calculate a threshold number of responses and nontoxicities at each stage for terminating a trial early when either of these quantities are low.

If a given observed x_{Rl} and x_{Tl} results in $PP_{Rl} < \theta_{RL}$ or $PP_{Tl} < \theta_{TL}$, then we recommend early termination of the trial at stage l due to futility. We therefore define C_{Rl} and C_{Tl} at each stage as the maximum x_{Rl} and x_{Tl} that result in trial termination due to futility:

$$C_{Rl} = \max \{x_{Rl}: PP_{Rl} < \theta_{RL}\}$$

$$C_{Tl} = \max \{x_{Tl}: PP_{Tl} < \theta_{TL}\}.$$

Since predictive probabilities are not as meaningful at the end of the trial, we define the cutoffs for trial success after the final stage using posterior probability:

$$C_{Rk} = \max \{x_{Rl}: (\text{posterior probability of } p_R > p_{R0}) < \theta_{RT}\}$$

$$C_{Tk} = \max \{x_{Tl}: (\text{posterior probability of } p_T > p_{T0}) < \theta_{TT}\}.$$

These calculations result in cutoffs for response and nontoxicity at each stage C_{R1}, \dots, C_{Rk} and C_{T1}, \dots, C_{Tk} that are completely separable and independent of the cutoffs for response.

Although there may be some potential for efficiency gains for nontoxicity cutoffs that depend on the observed number of responses and vice-versa, the discrete nature of participant response and nontoxicity would prevent much of these gains from being realized in practice. We also decided that it would be easier for clinical scientists and investigators to plan and execute a trial that had predetermined, fixed cutoffs at each stage. Instead, we focus on modelling the joint distribution of response and nontoxicity and resulting type 1 error, power, expected accrual, and probability of early termination to account for possible dependency between response and nontoxicity in Section 2.2.4.

2.2.3. Independent case

For simplicity, we continue our development of the joint testing framework assuming that response and nontoxicity are independent. In many phase 2 studies this is sufficient for the purposes of calculating sample sizes and often results in the same or similar power compared to when they are positively or negatively correlated (Bryant & Day, 1995). However, there are many situations where patients who are more likely to respond to treatment are also more (or less) likely to experience toxicity (Cook & Farewell, 1994; Hussaini et al., 2021; Das & Johnson, 2019; Teraoka et al., 2017) and researchers may want to model this explicitly when designing a trial. Later, in Section 2.2.4, we relax the assumption of independence and detail how these calculations change with dependent nontoxicity and response.

2.2.3.1. Distribution of response and nontoxicity counts

We define the joint distribution of x_{Rl} and x_{Tl} as a non-homogeneous Markov chain with a total of n_k^2 possible bivariate states $(x_{Rl}, x_{Tl}) = (0,0), \dots, (n_k, n_k)$ representing the range of possible values for x_{Rl} and x_{Tl} . The initial state is $(x_{Rl}, x_{Tl}) = (0,0)$. The transition probabilities for state $(x_{R(l-1)}, x_{T(l-1)})$ to (x_{Rl}, x_{Tl}) at stage l are defined as:

$$P_l(x_{Rl}, x_{Tl} | x_{R(l-1)}, x_{T(l-1)}, p_R, p_T)$$

$$= \begin{cases} \text{Bin}(x_{Rl} - x_{R(l-1)}; \delta_l, p_R) \text{Bin}(x_{Tl} - x_{T(l-1)}; \delta_l, p_T) & x_{R(l-1)} > C_{R(l-1)} \wedge x_{T(l-1)} > C_{T(l-1)} \\ 1 & o.w. \wedge x_{Rl} = x_{R(l-1)} \wedge x_{Tl} = x_{T(l-1)} \\ 0 & o.w. \end{cases}$$

where Bin is the binomial density. We use the product of binomials in the transition probabilities because response and nontoxicity are independent events.

To calculate the probabilities of observing x_R responses and x_T nontoxicities at the final stage k or any other stage in the trial we construct a vector $\mathbf{a} = (1, 0, \dots, 0)^T$ of length n_k^2 representing

the initial state where $P_0(x_{R0} = 0, x_{T0} = 0) = 1$ and $n_k^2 \times n_k^2$ matrices of the above transition probabilities at each stage, \mathbf{P}_l . We then calculate the vector of response probabilities at stage l , defined as

$$\mathbf{q}_l = \left(P_l(x_{Rl} = 0, x_{Tl} = 0 | p_R, p_T), \dots, P_l(x_{Rl} = n_k, x_{Tl} = n_k | p_R, p_T) \right)^T$$

by the following formula:

$$\mathbf{q}_l^T = \mathbf{a}^T \mathbf{P}_1 \cdots \mathbf{P}_l$$

which quickly yields the probabilities needed for type 1 and type 2 error and other metrics of trial performance.

2.2.3.2. Type 1 Error, Power, Expected Accrual, PET

Having derived the distribution of the response and nontoxicity counts, the marginal formulas for type I error and power become

$$\alpha_{R0} = P_{Rk}(x_{Rk} > C_{Rk} | p_{R0})$$

$$\alpha_{R1} = P_{Rk}(x_{Rk} > C_{Rk} | p_{R1})$$

$$\alpha_{T0} = P_{Tk}(x_{Tk} > C_{Tk} | p_{T0})$$

$$\alpha_{T1} = P_{Tk}(x_{Tk} > C_{Tk} | p_{T1}).$$

Where P_{Rk} and P_{Tk} are the marginal distributions of response and nontoxicity in the final stage. Under independence, the probabilities for type 1 error and power factor into the marginal probabilities:

$$\alpha_{00} = \alpha_{R0} \alpha_{T0}$$

$$\alpha_{01} = \alpha_{R0} \alpha_{T1}$$

$$\alpha_{10} = \alpha_{R1} \alpha_{T0}$$

$$\alpha_{11} = \alpha_{R1} \alpha_{T1}.$$

The distribution of the accrual, N , is closely related to the response and nontoxicity counts and the stage where the trial ends. Under independence, the distribution of accrual with respect to response and nontoxicity factors by the marginal distributions. The marginal distribution for accrual with respect to response is:

$$P(N = n_l | p_R) = P_{Rl}(C_{Rl-1} < x_{Rl} \leq C_{Rl} | p_R)$$

and the marginal distribution with respect to nontoxicity is

$$P(N = n_l | p_T) = P_{Tl}(C_{Tl-1} < x_{Tl} \leq C_{Tl} | p_T).$$

The expected accrual in the joint framework similarly factors by the marginal accrual probabilities under independence:

$$E_{00} = \sum_{l=1}^k n_l P(N = n_l | p_{R0}, p_{T0}) = \sum_{l=1}^k n_l P(N = n_l | p_{R0}) P(N = n_l | p_{T0})$$

$$\begin{aligned}
E_{01} &= \sum_{l=1}^k n_l P(N = n_l | p_{R0}, p_{T1}) = \sum_{l=1}^k n_l P(N = n_l | p_{R0}) P(N = n_l | p_{T1}) \\
E_{10} &= \sum_{l=1}^k n_l P(N = n_l | p_{R1}, p_{T0}) = \sum_{l=1}^k n_l P(N = n_l | p_{R1}) P(N = n_l | p_{T0}) \\
E_{11} &= \sum_{l=1}^k n_l P(N = n_l | p_{R1}, p_{T1}) = \sum_{l=1}^k n_l P(N = n_l | p_{R1}) P(N = n_l | p_{T1}).
\end{aligned}$$

The probability of early termination is also closely related to the distribution of accrual. The marginal probabilities of early termination are:

$$\begin{aligned}
PET_{R0} &= P(N < n_k | p_{R0}) = P_{R(k-1)}(x_{R(k-1)} \leq C_{R(k-1)} | p_{R0}) \\
PET_{R1} &= P(N < n_k | p_{R1}) = P_{R(k-1)}(x_{R(k-1)} \leq C_{R(k-1)} | p_{R1}) \\
PET_{T0} &= P(N < n_k | p_{T0}) = P_{T(k-1)}(x_{T(k-1)} \leq C_{T(k-1)} | p_{T0}) \\
PET_{T1} &= P(N < n_k | p_{T1}) = P_{T(k-1)}(x_{T(k-1)} \leq C_{T(k-1)} | p_{T1}).
\end{aligned}$$

Since in the joint framework early termination can occur either for insufficient response or nontoxicity, the probabilities of early termination are derived from the marginal probabilities:

$$\begin{aligned}
PET_{00} &= 1 - (1 - PET_{R0})(1 - PET_{T0}) \\
PET_{01} &= 1 - (1 - PET_{R0})(1 - PET_{T1}) \\
PET_{10} &= 1 - (1 - PET_{R1})(1 - PET_{T0}) \\
PET_{11} &= 1 - (1 - PET_{R1})(1 - PET_{T1}).
\end{aligned}$$

2.2.3.3. Trial design parameters

The design parameters for a trial consist of the sample size at each stage n_1, \dots, n_k (which also implies the number of stages, k) and the response count cutoffs for each stage C_{R1}, \dots, C_{Rk} and C_{T1}, \dots, C_{Tk} which can be uniquely determined by the posterior and predictive probability thresholds $\theta_{RT}, \theta_{RL}, \theta_{TT},$ and θ_{TL} . To run our method the user must first specify unacceptable and acceptable rates of response, p_{R0} and p_{R1} and nontoxicity p_{T0} and p_{T1} . Then, the user has the option to specify trial design parameters directly and calculate type 1 error α_{10} and α_{01} and power α_{11} , probability of early termination PET_{Ω} , and expected accrual E_{Ω} under this design, similar to Chen et al. (2019). Alternatively, the user can specify desired type 1 error rates α_R, α_T and power $(1 - \beta)$ and use our parameter search algorithm described in the next section to find trial design parameters which satisfy them. Our search returns a design that that satisfies these constraints while minimizing the final stage sample size n_k (minimax) and one that minimizes expected accrual E_{Ω} (optimal), similar to the Simon's two-stage design.

For either the fixed design input or the parameter search, the user has the option to specify beta-binomial distribution prior parameters for response a_R and b_R and nontoxicity a_T and b_T or use the defaults, $a_R = p_{R0}, b_R = 1 - p_{R0}, a_T = p_{T0},$ and $b_T = 1 - p_{T0}$ for the calculation of posterior probabilities. For the parameter search, the user also has the option to limit the number of trial stages k or to fix the size of each trial stage to a constant, δ .

2.2.3.4. Parameter Search Algorithm

We begin our parameter search algorithm by iterating over each possible value of the final stage sample size, n_k from n_{min} to n_{max} , which are specified by the user. For each value of n_k , we calculate the corresponding sample size for each intermediate stage $n_1, \dots, n_{(k-1)}$ by one of the following 2 rules:

1. $n_{(l+1)} - n_l = 1, \forall l \in \{1, \dots, k-1\}$, (or, alternatively, $n_{l+1} - n_l = \delta$ where δ is a constant)
2. Fix the number of stages k to a constant value and determine all possible stage sizes that satisfy $n_1 < \dots < n_k$.

Then, for each unique vector n_1, \dots, n_k , we calculate the grid of $\theta_{RL}, \theta_{RT}, \theta_{TL}, \theta_{TT}$ to search over. Because of the discrete nature of the number of participants and the number of responses at each trial stage, there are a finite number of combinations of θ_{RL}, θ_{RT} that change the cutoffs C_{R1}, \dots, C_{Rk} and θ_{TL}, θ_{TT} that change C_{T1}, \dots, C_{Tk} . We quickly calculate the grid of θ_{RL}, θ_{RT} and θ_{TL}, θ_{TT} by the following formulas:

$$(\theta_{RL}, \theta_{RT}) = \left(\sum_{j=i}^{m_l=n_k-n_l} P(Y_R = m_l - j | x_{Rl}), \int_{p_{R0}}^1 \frac{p^{a_R+x_{Rl}+i-1}(1-p)^{b_R+n_k-x_{Rl}-i-1}}{B(a_R+x_{Rl}+i, b_R+n_k-x_{Rl}-i)} dp \right)$$

$$\forall x_{Rl} \in \{0, \dots, n_l\}, i \in \{0, \dots, n_k - n_l\} \forall l \in \{1, \dots, k\}$$

$$(\theta_{TL}, \theta_{TT}) = \left(\sum_{j=i}^{m_l=n_k-n_l} P(Y_T = m_l - j | x_{Tl}), \int_{p_{T0}}^1 \frac{p^{a_T+x_{Tl}+i-1}(1-p)^{b_T+n_k-x_{Tl}-i-1}}{B(a_T+x_{Tl}+i, b_T+n_k-x_{Tl}-i)} dp \right)$$

$$\forall x_{Tl} \in \{0, \dots, n_l\}, i \in \{0, \dots, n_k - n_l\} \forall l \in \{1, \dots, k\}$$

where $P(Y_R = m_l - j | x_{Rl})$ and $P(Y_T = m_l - j | x_{Tl})$ are as defined in Section 2.2.2. This calculation yields pairs of threshold values θ_{RL}, θ_{RT} that each specify a unique vector of cutoffs C_{R1}, \dots, C_{Rk} and pairs θ_{TL}, θ_{TT} that specify C_{T1}, \dots, C_{Tk} by the formulas in Section 2.2.2.

Then, for each pair θ_{RL}, θ_{RT} in θ_{RL}, θ_{RT} , we determine which pairs satisfy the desired type 1 error for response α_R and power $1 - \beta$. The bound for marginal type 1 error can be relaxed to satisfy $\alpha_{R0} \leq \alpha_R / (1 - \beta)$ since $\alpha_{01} = \alpha_{R0} \alpha_{T1}$ and $\alpha_{T1} \geq 1 - \beta$. We use the following property to avoid calculating the expected type 1 error rate α_{R0} and power α_{R1} for each pair:

Given $n_1, \dots, n_k, a_R, b_R$, if $\theta_{RL} \leq \theta'_{RL}$ and $\theta_{RT} \leq \theta'_{RT}$, then $C_{Rl} \leq C'_{Rl} \forall l \in \{1, \dots, k\}$.

Since $P_{Rl}(x_{Rl} > C_{Rl} | p_R) \geq P_{Rl}(x_{Rl} > C'_{Rl} | p_R)$ when $C_{Rl} \leq C'_{Rl}$, it therefore follows that $\alpha_{R0} \geq \alpha'_{R0}$ and $\alpha_{R1} \geq \alpha'_{R1}$ when $\theta_{RL} \leq \theta'_{RL}$ and $\theta_{RT} \leq \theta'_{RT}$. Therefore, in order to save computational time, we infer $\alpha'_{R0} \leq \alpha_R / (1 - \beta)$ for any pair $\theta'_{RL}, \theta'_{RT}$ when we have already determined there is a pair θ_{RL}, θ_{RT} with $\alpha_{R0} \leq \alpha_R / (1 - \beta)$. Similarly, we infer $\alpha_{R1} > 1 - \beta$ for any pair θ_{RL}, θ_{RT} when we have already determined there is a pair $\theta'_{RL}, \theta'_{RT}$ with $\alpha'_{R1} > 1 - \beta$. Otherwise, we calculate them using the formulas in Section 2.2.3.2.

We follow the same process to determine pairs θ_{TL}, θ_{TT} in θ_{TL}, θ_{TT} which satisfy the desired type 1 error for nontoxicity α_T and power $1 - \beta$. Then, for all combinations of θ_{RL}, θ_{RT} and θ_{TL}, θ_{TT} that passed the marginal bounds we check if these also satisfy the joint bounds in Section 2.2.1.

After identifying these combinations of pairs of thresholds θ_{RL}, θ_{RT} and θ_{TL}, θ_{TT} (and, consequently, vectors of stage sizes n_1, \dots, n_k) that satisfy the desired type 1 error and power, we can calculate the expected accrual E_Ω for these feasible trial designs. The combination of $n_1, \dots, n_k, \theta_{RL}, \theta_{RT}, \theta_{TL},$ and θ_{TT} with the overall smallest E_Ω is denoted the optimal design and we return these parameters. Users may also be interested in the combination of parameters with the smallest final stage sample size n_k , but for a given trial there can be several feasible combinations of $n_1, \dots, n_k, \theta_{RL}, \theta_{RT}, \theta_{TL},$ and θ_{TT} that all share the same minimal value for n_k . For this reason, we return the combination of parameters with the smallest feasible n_k that also minimizes E_Ω as the minimax design for the proposed trial.

2.2.4. Dependent case

2.2.4.1. Odds Ratio

We continue our development of the joint testing framework by relaxing the assumption of independent response and nontoxicity. Assuming a fixed odds ratio ϕ for response and nontoxicity, define

$$\begin{aligned} p_{11} &= P(\text{response, nontoxicity}) \\ p_{10} &= P(\text{response, toxicity}) \\ p_{01} &= P(\text{no response, nontoxicity}) \\ p_{00} &= P(\text{no response, toxicity}) \\ \phi &= \frac{p_{00}p_{11}}{p_{01}p_{10}}. \end{aligned}$$

The joint probabilities $p_{11}, p_{10}, p_{01},$ and p_{00} are calculated from the marginal probabilities $p_R, p_T,$ and the odds ratio ϕ by the following formulas (Epstein, 2022):

$$\begin{aligned} S &= \sqrt{(1 + (p_T + p_R) + (\phi - 1))^2 + 4\phi(1 - \phi)p_T p_R} \\ p_{11} &= \frac{1 + (p_T + p_R)(\phi - 1) - S}{2(\phi - 1)} \\ p_{01} &= p_T - p_{11} \\ p_{10} &= p_R - p_{11} \\ p_{00} &= 1 - p_{01} - p_{10} - p_{11} \end{aligned}$$

The relationship between the joint and the marginal probabilities of response and nontoxicity are also summarized in [Figure 3](#).

2.2.4.2. Distribution of response and nontoxicity counts

In the dependent case, each individual in each stage of the trial can have one of four outcomes: both response and nontoxicity, response and toxicity, no response and nontoxicity, or no response and toxicity. Within each stage, the counts of these four events follow the multinomial distribution with probabilities $p_{11}, p_{10}, p_{01},$ and p_{00} . In our framework only the total numbers of responses and nontoxicities are relevant to the outcome of the trial and not these finer-scale

events. Therefore, the joint distribution of x_{Rl} and x_{Tl} in the dependent case is also a non-homogeneous Markov chain with the same state space as in the independent case described in Section 2.2.3.1. The main difference is that the transition probabilities for state $(x_{R(l-1)}, x_{T(l-1)})$ to (x_{Rl}, x_{Tl}) at stage l are defined as the sum over the multinomial probabilities of all possible configurations of the joint events that satisfy those counts. First, we define $i = x_{Rl} - x_{R(l-1)}$ and $j = x_{Tl} - x_{T(l-1)}$ to simplify the notation. Then the transition probability becomes:

$$P_{\phi l}(x_{Rl}, x_{Tl} | x_{R(l-1)}, x_{T(l-1)}, p_R, p_T, \phi) = \begin{cases} \sum_{g=\max(0, i+j-\delta_l)}^{\min(i, j)} \text{Multi}(g, j-g, i-g, \delta_l - i - j + g; \delta_l, p_{11}, p_{01}, p_{10}, p_{00}) & x_{R(l-1)} > C_{R(l-1)} \wedge x_{T(l-1)} > C_{T(l-1)} \\ 1 & o.w. \wedge x_{Rl} = x_{R(l-1)} \wedge x_{Tl} = x_{T(l-1)} \\ 0 & o.w. \end{cases}$$

where *Multi* indicates the multinomial density and ϕ is the odds ratio. This formula for the transition probability accounts for the dependence between x_{Rl} and x_{Tl} because the value of ϕ is reflected in the joint event probabilities p_{11} , p_{10} , p_{01} , and p_{00} . The calculation of the probability of observing x_R responses and x_T nontoxicities at the final stage k or any other stage in the trial then proceeds as in Section 2.2.3.1, only substituting $\mathbf{P}_{\phi l}$ for \mathbf{P}_l .

2.2.4.3. Type 1 Error, Power, Expected Accrual, PET

In the dependent case, the calculation of type 1 error and power is based on the joint probability of the response counts and cannot be factored out if $\phi \neq 1$. Instead, we sum over the joint probabilities of the response and nontoxicity counts as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \alpha_{00} &= P_{\phi k}(x_{Rk} > C_{Rk}, x_{Tk} > C_{Tk} | p_{R0}, p_{T0}, \phi) \\ \alpha_{01} &= P_{\phi k}(x_{Rk} > C_{Rk}, x_{Tk} > C_{Tk} | p_{R0}, p_{T1}, \phi) \\ \alpha_{10} &= P_{\phi k}(x_{Rk} > C_{Rk}, x_{Tk} > C_{Tk} | p_{R1}, p_{T0}, \phi) \\ \alpha_{11} &= P_{\phi k}(x_{Rk} > C_{Rk}, x_{Tk} > C_{Tk} | p_{R1}, p_{T1}, \phi). \end{aligned}$$

Similar to type 1 error and power, the accrual probabilities also cannot be factored out if $\phi \neq 1$ so we sum over the joint probabilities of x_{Rl} and x_{Tl} in a given stage as follows:

$$P(N = n_l | p_R, p_T, \phi) = P_{\phi l}(C_{R(l-1)} < x_{Rl} \leq C_{Rl} \wedge C_{T(l-1)} < x_{Tl} \leq C_{Tl} | p_R, p_T, \phi).$$

Expected accrual also does not factor when $\phi \neq 1$ so we simply sum up the size of each stage times the joint probability of stopping on that stage to calculate it:

$$\begin{aligned} E_{00} &= \sum_{l=1}^k n_l P(N = n_l | p_{R0}, p_{T0}, \phi) \\ E_{01} &= \sum_{l=1}^k n_l P(N = n_l | p_{R0}, p_{T1}, \phi) \end{aligned}$$

$$E_{10} = \sum_{l=1}^k n_l P(N = n_l | p_{R1}, p_{T0}, \phi)$$

$$E_{11} = \sum_{l=1}^k n_l P(N = n_l | p_{R1}, p_{T1}, \phi).$$

As elsewhere in the dependent case, the probabilities of early termination cannot be factored out by the marginal probabilities when $\phi \neq 1$ so we sum over the joint accrual probabilities to obtain them:

$$PET_{00} = P_{\phi l}(N < n_k | p_{R0}, p_{T0}, \phi)$$

$$PET_{01} = P_{\phi l}(N < n_k | p_{R0}, p_{T1}, \phi)$$

$$PET_{10} = P_{\phi l}(N < n_k | p_{R1}, p_{T0}, \phi)$$

$$PET_{11} = P_{\phi l}(N < n_k | p_{R1}, p_{T1}, \phi).$$

2.2.4.4. Trial Design Parameters

Trial design parameters are identical to those described in Section 2.2.3.3 except that an odds ratio ϕ must be specified to model the dependence between response and nontoxicity.

2.2.4.5. Parameter Search Algorithm

Constructing the grid of parameters $n_1, \dots, n_k, \theta_{RL}, \theta_{RT}, \theta_{TL},$ and θ_{TT} to search over in the dependent case is identical to the algorithm for the independent case described in Section 2.2.3.4. However, since the joint probabilities for type 1 error and power no longer factor by the marginal probabilities in the dependent case, we can no longer search over pairs of θ_{RL}, θ_{RT} , independently from θ_{TL}, θ_{TT} . Instead, we search over the Cartesian product of the pairs of parameter vectors, $(\theta_{RL}, \theta_{RT}) \times (\theta_{TL}, \theta_{TT})$. Although the search space is much larger than in the independent case, we can still apply a similar, multivariate process to avoid calculating type 1 error and power on the entire search space. We infer $\alpha'_{01} \leq \alpha_R$ for any quartet $\theta'_{RL}, \theta'_{RT}, \theta'_{TL}, \theta'_{TT}$ when we have already determined there is a quartet $\theta_{RL} \leq \theta'_{RL}, \theta_{RT} \leq \theta'_{RT}, \theta_{TL} \leq \theta'_{TL}, \theta_{TT} \leq \theta'_{TT}$ with $\alpha_{01} \leq \alpha_R$, and we infer $\alpha'_{10} \leq \alpha_T$ for any quartet $\theta'_{RL}, \theta'_{RT}, \theta'_{TL}, \theta'_{TT}$ when we have already determined there is a quartet $\theta_{RL} \leq \theta'_{RL}, \theta_{RT} \leq \theta'_{RT}, \theta_{TL} \leq \theta'_{TL}, \theta_{TT} \leq \theta'_{TT}$ with $\alpha_{10} \leq \alpha_T$. For power, we infer $\alpha_{11} \geq 1 - \beta$ for any quartet $\theta_{RL}, \theta_{RT}, \theta_{TL}, \theta_{TT}$ when we have already determined there is a quartet $\theta'_{RL} \geq \theta_{RL}, \theta'_{RT} \geq \theta_{RT}, \theta'_{TL} \geq \theta_{TL}, \theta'_{TT} \geq \theta_{TT}$ with $\alpha'_{11} \geq 1 - \beta$. The calculation of expected accrual, E_{Ω} , and definition of the optimal and minimax designs are identical to the independent case described in Section 2.2.3.4.

3. An Illustrative Example: Bryant and Day Example

To illustrate the effectiveness of our method, we use the example of a 2-stage trial for both response and nontoxicity endpoints described in Bryant & Day (1995). In this example, the desired type 1 error for both response and nontoxicity are 15% ($\alpha_R = \alpha_T = 0.15$) and power is 85% ($1 - \beta = 0.85$). The unacceptable and acceptable rates of response are $p_{R0} = 0.3, p_{R1} = 0.5$ and for nontoxicity are $p_{T0} = 0.6, p_{T1} = 0.8$ and they are independent with odds ratio $\phi =$

1. A design with a single interim analysis at $n_1 = 19$ and final analysis at $n_k = 33$ with response cutoffs $C_{R1} = 5, C_{R2} = 12$ and nontoxicity cutoffs $C_{T1} = 11, C_{T2} = 22$ satisfies this. Selecting predictive and posterior probability thresholds $\theta_{RL} = \theta_{TL} = 0.1$ and $\theta_{RT} = \theta_{TT} = 0.8$ for both response and nontoxicity lead to this identical design. The expected trial performance based on these parameters is: response type 1 error rate, $\alpha_{10} = 0.146$; nontoxicity type 1 error rate, $\alpha_{01} = 0.145$; power, $\alpha_{11} = 0.854$; expected accrual, $E_{\Omega} = 26.2$, and probability of early termination, $PET_{\Omega} = 0.486$.

Since the sample size required for many clinical trials is calculated with respect to efficacy only and not both efficacy and safety, we wanted to evaluate the effect this would have on the above example. We used our parameter search algorithm to design a trial for a single efficacy endpoint that would satisfy type 1 error for response $\alpha_R = 0.15$ and power $1 - \beta = 0.85$ with unacceptable response rate $p_{R0} = 0.3$ and acceptable rate $p_{R1} = 0.5$ with only 1 interim analysis. Our algorithm found that a design with parameters $n_1 = 10, n_2 = 27, \theta_{RL} = 0.0462$, and $\theta_{RT} = 0.8704$ resulted in a trial with cutoffs $C_{R1} = 2, C_{R2} = 10$, expected accrual $E_{R0} = 20.5$ and probability of early termination $PET_{R0} = 0.383$. Assuming the same underlying unacceptable and acceptable nontoxicity probabilities in the Bryant & Day example, p_{T0} and p_{T1} , we present the effect that a range of different cutoffs for nontoxicity that might be applied to the interim and final analyses on trial performance in [Table 1](#). In this example, naively designing the trial and determining sample size for only response or nontoxicity while testing for both results in an overestimation of trial performance and a trial that is underpowered.

In order to illustrate the different effects that the thresholds for predictive probability θ_{RL} and posterior probability θ_{RT} have on the response cutoffs C_{R1}, \dots, C_{Rk} , we have plotted the cutoffs for different values of θ_{RL} and θ_{RT} in [Figure 4](#). This illustrates that the posterior probability threshold θ_{RT} primarily affects the cutoff applied at the end of the trial while the predictive probability threshold has little influence on the cutoff at the end of the trial but attenuates the cutoffs applied at earlier stages of the trial. The predictive probability approach tends to be more stringent in the early stages of the trial than basing the cutoffs on the posterior probability alone ([Lee & Liu, 2008](#)). The combination of θ_{RL} and θ_{RT} allows for a wide range of possibilities for potential trial designs that can be more stringent in the early stages of the trial (resulting in a high probability of early termination under the null) or make the later stages more decisive for trial success when there is less variability in the estimate of the response rate p_R .

One difference between our method and the one described in Bryant & Day, 1995 is the ability to add additional interim analyses to the trial. Holding $n_k, \theta_{RL}, \theta_{TL}, \theta_{RT}$, and θ_{TT} constant, we added additional, equally-spaced stages to the trial from $k = 1$ (no interim analyses) to $k = 16$ and evaluated the effect on type 1 error, power, probability of early termination, and expected accrual, with the results presented in [Figure 5](#). While the relationship between k and the 4 measures of trial performance is not monotone due to the discrete nature of the number of participants, responses, and nontoxicities, the general trend is for additional interim analyses to result in a lower probability of eventual trial success. Increasing k results in lower type 1 error, power, and expected accrual with higher probability of early termination, though this effect diminishes after $k = 12$. In order to satisfy the requirements for type 1 error and power specified in the example, the predictive and posterior probability thresholds $\theta_{RL}, \theta_{TL}, \theta_{RT}$, and θ_{TT} would need to be adjusted. Additional interim analyses allows for achieving a higher probability of

early termination and lower expected accrual while satisfying the same type 1 error and power but the discrete nature of the trial limits these gains.

When response and nontoxicity cannot be assumed to be independent events, our method allows specifying an odds ratio ϕ to model this dependence. Holding $n_1, n_2, \theta_{RL}, \theta_{TL}, \theta_{RT},$ and θ_{TT} constant, we varied ϕ from 0.0001 to 10,000 and evaluated the effect on trial performance, with the results presented in Figure 6. Increasing the odds ratio resulted in a higher probability of trial success as reflected in the type 1 error rate, power, probability of early termination and expected accrual, but the effect diminishes for $\phi > 1000$ or $\phi < 0.001$. Assuming independence when $\phi < 1$ results in a conservative trial design that is potentially underpowered but trial parameters will need to be adjusted when $\phi > 1$ in order to satisfy the desired type 1 error rate for the trial.

4. DISCUSSION

We have introduced a novel method for phase II studies that uses Bayesian predictive probability to design a joint study of efficacy and safety with interim analyses at any number of arbitrary points in the trial. In addition, our flexible framework allows modelling dependence between response and nontoxicity by specifying an odds ratio ϕ . Our method provides for the optimization of trial design parameters with respect to the expected accrual or maximum number of patients enrolled in the trial.

Using Bayesian predictive probabilities to determine cutoffs for response and nontoxicity at interim analyses has several advantages over Bayesian posterior and frequentist-based cutoffs. There is more uncertainty in the posterior probability of success in the early stages of a trial than in the predictive probability, so cutoffs based on posterior probability tend to be anticonservative in early stages compared to the predictive probability cutoffs. Trials designed using posterior probabilities in this way have a lower probability of early termination compared to using the predicted probability design (Lee & Liu, 2008). Frequentist-based cutoffs, like those in (Simon, 1989) and (Bryant & Day, 1995) work well for two-stage designs because there are unique cutoffs for the interim analysis and the final stage that minimize either expected accrual or final sample size while satisfying constraints on type 1 error and power. However, for a more flexible design with arbitrary interim analyses, there are several patterns of cutoffs at the various stages that result in similar type 1 error, power, expected accrual and maximum sample size such that the problem is no longer identifiable without additional constraints. The Bayesian predictive probability framework provides a unique solution to calculating the cutoffs at each interim analysis that perform well compared to the frequentist two-stage designs, particularly when additional interim analyses are conducted. The beta-binomial prior in the Bayesian predictive probability presented here can be set to a weak setting ($a + b \ll 1$) so that the observed response and nontoxicity counts are given more weight in the calculation than the prior.

Our method specifies independent cutoffs for response and nontoxicity at each trial stage. That is, regardless of the number of responses observed at an interim analysis, the number of observed nontoxicities must still exceed the predefined cutoff C_{TL} in order for the trial to proceed to the next stage, even when nontoxicity and response are not independent. An alternative strategy could have been to apply a single cutoff to a function of the number of observed responses and nontoxicities rather than separate cutoffs for each individually. Such a function could account for situations where a trial should continue when there is low nontoxicity and high response or high

nontoxicity and low response, resulting in less conservative criteria for interim analyses that would still satisfy constraints on type 1 error and power at the end of the study. Despite these advantages, we decided that predetermined cutoffs for response and nontoxicity separately would be easier for the study team to understand at the trial design phase, describe in a study protocol, and implement once the trial is under way. In addition, because of the discrete nature of response and nontoxicity in the trial, it is unlikely that applying a less conservative joint cutoff would impact the expected accrual, maximum sample size, or probability of early termination by any meaningful amount.

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6. TABLES

n_1, n_2	10, 27	10, 27	10, 27	10, 27
θ_{RL}, θ_{RT}	0.046, 0.870	0.046, 0.870	0.046, 0.870	0.046, 0.870
C_{R1}, C_{R2}	2, 10	2, 10	2, 10	2, 10
C_{T1}, C_{T2}	—	3, 16	4, 18	5, 20
α_{10}	0.146	0.144	0.135	0.103
α_{01}	—	0.388	0.155	0.035
Power α_{11}	0.851	0.841	0.787	0.604
PET_{Ω}	0.383	0.107	0.212	0.402
E_{Ω}	20.5	25.2	23.4	20.2

Table 1: Effect of various choices of nontoxicity cutoffs on trial performance.

7. FIGURES

	Unacceptable Response $x_{Rl} \leq C_{Rl}$	Acceptable Response $x_{Rl} > C_{Rl}$
Unacceptable Nontoxicity $x_{Tl} \leq C_{Tl}$	H_{00} Terminate trial due to both	H_{10} Terminate trial due to poor toxicity
Acceptable Nontoxicity $x_{Tl} > C_{Tl}$	H_{01} Terminate trial due to poor response	H_{11} Continue trial, or Success if $l = k$

Figure 1: Decision matrix for response and nontoxicity at each stage.

	Unacceptable Response p_{R0}	Acceptable Response p_{R1}	
Unacceptable Nontoxicity p_{T0}	α_{00} PET_{00} E_{00}	α_{10} PET_{10} E_{10}	α_{T0} PET_{T0} E_{T0}
Acceptable Nontoxicity p_{T1}	α_{01} PET_{01} E_{01}	α_{11} PET_{11} E_{11}	α_{T1} PET_{T1} E_{T1}
	α_{R0} PET_{R0} E_{R0}	α_{R1} PET_{R1} E_{R1}	

Figure 2: Notation matrix for joint trial of response and nontoxicity.

	No Response	Response	
Toxicity	p_{00}	p_{10}	$1 - p_T$
Nontoxicity	p_{01}	p_{11}	p_T
	$1 - p_R$	p_R	

Figure 3: Table of the joint and marginal probabilities of response and nontoxicity.

Figure 4: Effect of changing thresholds for predictive probability θ_{RL} (left) and posterior probability θ_{RT} (right) on response cutoffs C_{R1}, \dots, C_{Rk} . Assumes an interim analysis is conducted with every new patient enrolled in the trial.

Figure 5: Effect of number of equally-sized trial stages on expected performance.

Figure 6: Effect of odds ratio on expected trial performance.